

Traditional Knowledge in Sustainable Development of India and Brazil: A Comparative Analysis

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Traditional knowledge refers to the knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous and local communities around the world. It tends to be collectively owned and takes the form of stories, songs, folklore, proverbs, cultural values, beliefs, rituals, community laws, local language and agricultural practices, including the development of plant species and animal breeds. Traditional knowledge is mainly of a practical nature, particularly in such fields as agriculture, fisheries, health, horticulture, forestry and environmental management in general. At present, unsustainable development has led to global warming, environmental destruction, conflict, poverty and hunger, vast inequalities and social instability. It is noteworthy that the traditional knowledge possessed by indigenous communities across the globe may be the 'key drivers' for poverty reduction, livelihood improvement and attaining sustainability of the given environment. Hence, this study aims to compare the use of traditional knowledge in achieving sustainable development by two foremost countries of the BRICS grouping, that is, Brazil and India. At present, Brazil is ranked 50th and India 112th amongst 166 countries as per the Sustainable Development Report 2023. Thus it becomes pertinent for both the countries to harness the diverse domain of indigenous knowledge in order to achieve a balance between economic growth and clean environment to meet the 2030 deadline for achieving Sustainable Development Goals.

Keywords: Traditional Knowledge, Sustainable Development, Knowledge Economy, Emerging Markets, Global South as Hub of Indigenous Knowledge, Economy vs Environment etc.